

Topic: CIRC BIO-01-01 Circular Cities and Regions Initiative's project development assistance (CCRI-PDA)

D4.1 - PDA set-up teams, governance structure and processes

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D4.1 PDA set-up teams, governance structure and processes

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Abstract	This deliverable describes the teams established for each Project Development Assistance (PDA) and their governance structure and processes.	
Title and number of connected deliverables	D3.2 – PDAs implementation models, operational services and financing schemes	
Explain Deliverable Dependency/ Connection	This deliverable includes the setup of all pilots' Managing teams for making operative the PDA according to the operational services identified within WP3. Each team includes experts with administrative issues, financial aspects, legal issues, risk mitigation, validation, evaluation, and monitoring; other specific expertise is included according to the needs of each pilot.	
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1. Objective and Purpose

The project DEvelopers of Circular SOLutions (DECISO) aims to support the delivery of services for projects that focus on developing circular economy at local and regional scales, setting up four pilots in Hamburg (Germany), Alentejo (Portugal), Northwest Germany (Germany) and West Macedonia (Greece), covering different sectors: waste, water, energy and agri-food.

The WP4 of the DECISO Project includes the following Objectives:

- Set up operative managing structure in each pilot,
- Define Launch strategies from the pilots,
- Plan the operative steps,
- Collect Grant Agreements signed with the winners in the programmes.

Task 4.1 is dedicated to support the pilots:

- to set up the pilot Managing Team (in an appropriate and tailored made structure),
- to decide their own governance structure and processes for their Managing Team.

The project consulted through research the available public content by CCRI for the DECISO PDA needs during their work on Task 3.2: Implementation model and operational services. All partners were informed in detail on PDA in circular economy working in Task 3.2 as also for the production of the Deliverable: D3.2: Description of the PDA implementation model and operational service for each pilot. The responsible partner for Task 3.2 provided the Guide to Understanding and Tailoring PDA for the 4 Pilot Regions.

Additional information on PDA will be provided in D3.2.

Deliverable 4.1 relates to Deliverable 3.2: PDAs implementation models, operational services and financing schemes that have a concrete description of the PDA structure. An abstract of its purpose and structure is following to showcase the connection with D4.1:

Each pilot region has identified a specific theme where they aim to create circular economy projects. These projects are designed to address local challenges and capitalize on opportunities unique to each region. To support the pilot regions in this endeavour, the DECISO project aids in several key areas: financial advice, legal advice and risk mitigation advice.

As a follow-up of the activities followed in task 3.2 that resulted to deliverable 3.2, each pilot set up a Managing team for making operative the Project Development Assistance (PDA) according to the operational services identified related to building business plans in each pilot. Each team includes staff members and experts in administrative issues, financial aspects, legal issues, risk mitigation, validation, evaluation and monitoring. In addition, other specific expertise can be included according to each pilot's needs. The managing teams are mainly composed of personnel of the organisations, but some of the activities require external experts.

The deliverable aims to introduce the Managing Teams established for each pilot PDA and their governance structure and processes.

The purpose is to establish the Managing Teams and to make operative the PDA according to the operational services identified by each pilot.

The core steps followed for the development of this Deliverable are described in section 2 and depicted in Figure 1.

2. Description of the Steps followed & the suggested Framework

For the development of the deliverable, the authors' team of the responsible Task leader [Municipality District Heating of Amynteo (MDHA)] followed 4 Steps:

Step 1. Desk research to set the framework of the Managing Teams governance structure model. The bibliography and sitography are included in the Annex.

Step 2. The Task leader consulted the proposed PDA framework and governance structure with each pilot and customised it to each one specific needs.

Step 3. All pilots identified their PDA governance needs and customised their governance model based on the common framework provided at the project level.

Step 4. The deliverable developed based on each pilot PDA contribution to their personalised governance structure model and processes.

Figure 1: Steps followed for the development of Deliverable 4.1

2.1 Tool with related framework & suggestions to Set up the managing teams

The Task leader provided to all pilots a document as a tool, that included the related framework & suggestions to Set up the managing teams.

Pilots' decisions are included in "Section 3: Pilots' PDA Managing Teams". The content of this tool provided to all pilots is described in the next subsections.

Introduction

Using the business plans produced in other work packages of the project, DECISO partners are working on WP4 tasks for:

- setting-up the operative managing structure in each pilot,
- defining the Launch strategies from the pilots and,
- planning the operative steps of each pilot

Task 4.1 is dedicated to supporting the pilots:

- to set up the pilot Managing Teams (in an appropriate and tailor-made structure)
- to decide their own governance structure and processes for their Managing Team

Circular Economy PDA Framework for use in DECISO project

Project Development Assistance (PDA) is a specialized service designed to support organizations, governments, and stakeholders in the effective planning, development, and implementation of projects. It involves providing expertise, guidance, and resources to ensure that projects are strategically designed, economically viable, and aligned with specific objectives.

In the context of Circular Economy projects, the objective/function of PDA is to facilitate the transition towards circular practices, sustainable resource management, and waste reduction. PDA aims to promote the adoption of circular economy principles, such as recycling, reusing, and remanufacturing, to minimize waste and environmental impact while fostering economic growth.

The services offered by PDA for each DECISO pilot are described in WP3.

Each pilot will set up a Managing team to make operative the PDA according to the operational services identified within WP3.

Each one of the four PDA Managing Teams should include experts with:

- administrative issues,
- financial aspects,
- legal issues,
- technical aspects,
- risks mitigation,
- evaluation, monitoring and validation,
- other (identified by each partner).

Comment:

The Managing Teams will be mainly composed by personnel of the promoters, but some activities could require external experts.

A critical definition for DECISO PDA Managing Teams is “Maturity”:

"Project maturity in terms of planning, business model, financial and legal structure as well as the project of reaching the financial close within a predefined period of time not exceeding a specific timeline after the award decision".

Methodology

To set up the pilot managing teams (in an appropriate and tailored made structure) all pilots need to fill a table based on their pilot implementation needs. The [Table 11](#) is included in Annex I, followed by some examples of DECISO PDA Managing teams’ tasks and responsibilities.

2.2 Document as a starting point to support the Steps 2 & 3

The Task leader also provided a document to all pilots with the following content as a starting point to support the Steps 2 & 3.

Pilots' decisions are included in "[Section 4: Governance structure and processes](#)"

Services Offered by DECISO PDA Managing Teams:

Each one of the DECISO Project Development Assistance Managing Teams will offer a range of services to support the circular economy initiatives of the pilots and enhance their project success.

These services will mainly include:

- **Project Identification:** Identifying potential circular economy projects relevant to the regional context and aligning with local priorities.
- **Feasibility Studies:** Conducting in-depth assessments to evaluate the viability, benefits, and risks associated with proposed projects.
- **Stakeholder Engagement:** Facilitating dialogue and collaboration among various stakeholders, including governments, businesses, NGOs, and local communities.
- **Technical Expertise:** Providing specialized knowledge in circular economy practices, waste management, resource efficiency, and sustainable technologies.
- **Financial Planning:** Assisting in budgeting, resource allocation, and identifying funding sources for project implementation.
- **Legal and Regulatory Guidance:** Ensuring compliance with regional and national laws and regulations related to circular economy initiatives.
- **Monitoring and Evaluation:** Establishing mechanisms to track project progress, measure impact, and make data-driven decisions for continuous improvement.

DECISO Governance structure and processes Framework

The core objectives of the DECISO PDA Managing teams are:

- to improve the pilot's maturity for subsequent calls for proposals through high-quality technical and financial advisory support tailored to the pilots' needs;
- mainly to support the project(s) awarded with a contract, to be successfully implemented and entry into operation.

Establishing a governance structure is critical for the success of any project. This structure helps define the roles, responsibilities, and decision-making processes to ensure accountability, transparency, and effective collaboration among the Managing Team members.

The governance structure suggested defines roles, responsibilities, and decision-making processes.

Each DECISO promoter will establish a governance structure for the pilot implementation that will include at least the Processes P1 to P7 with the use of the following template. The template that was prepared and provided includes the titles of the processes' objectives.

Table 1: DECISO Governance structure and processes Framework

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • P1. Monitoring the Key goals – indicators & the projects’ alignment with the organisation
<p>Objectives of the process:</p> <p>To overview the: Key goals – indicators to achieve as planned for the project and to manage the:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project alignment with organisational strategy, risk management, compliance, and efficient decision-making.
<p>Responsible PDA member for P1: Name of the person</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • P2. Monitoring the Coordination with the Key Stakeholders
<p>Objective of the process:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To monitor the coordination with the identified relevant key stakeholders list (input from WP2)
<p>Responsible PDA member for P2: Name of the person</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • P3. Monitoring the projects’ Roles and Responsibilities
<p>Objectives of the process:</p> <p>To overview & monitor the Specific roles and Responsibilities' effectiveness:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project Manager: Responsible for day-to-day planning, execution, and monitoring of the project. • Project Team Members: Carry out specific tasks and contribute to the project's overall success. • Steering Committee: Provides strategic guidance and decision-making authority.
<p>Responsible PDA member for P3: Name of the person</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • P4. Monitoring the projects’ Decision-Making Processes
<p>Objectives of the process:</p> <p>To overview & monitor the activities foreseen:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Levels of authority for different roles • Decisions require approval from higher levels
<p>Responsible PDA member for P4: Name of the person</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • P5. Monitoring the projects’ Risk Management
<p>Objective of the process:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overview & monitor the projects’ risk management plan
<p>Responsible for P5: Name of the person</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • P6. Monitoring the Projects’ Internal Communication Plan
<p>Objectives of the process:</p> <p>Overview & monitor the activities foreseen, in terms of:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Frequency • Channels of communication • Types of information to be communicated
<p>Responsible for P6: Name of the person</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • P7. Monitoring the Meeting Protocols
<p>Objective of the process:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overview & monitor the protocols for meetings, including frequency, agenda creation, and reporting mechanisms.
<p>Responsible for P7: Name of the person</p>

The suggested following Graph visualises each DECISO Pilot Processes

Figure 2: DECISO pilot processes

The suggested Processes are the following:

- P1: Monitoring the Key goals – indicators & the projects’ alignment with the organisation
- P2: Monitoring the Coordination with the Key Stakeholders
- P3: Monitoring the projects’ Roles and Responsibilities
- P4: Monitoring the projects’ Decision-Making Processes
- P5: Monitoring the projects’ Risk Management
- P6: Monitoring the Projects’ Internal Communication Plan
- P7: Monitoring the Meeting Protocols

Project Cycle Model

The Governance structure and processes should follow the Project Cycle Model of each Pilot.

Figure 3: Project Cycle Model

Table 2: Project cycle stages

Project cycle stage	Short description
Identification	Definition of the “problem”. Generation of possible project ideas (alternatives).
Preparation	Development of detailed project proposal.
Appraisal	Project proposal appraisal by the potential funder.
Funding	Formal agreement on funding the project between the funder and the proposer.
Implementation & monitoring	Project is carried out according to the contract or other agreements made. Internal monitoring and external reporting is carried out.
Evaluation	Assessment of project results against its original objectives in terms of its performance, efficiency and impact.

The time needed for each stage of project identification, preparation and appraisal varies greatly depending on the size and complexity of the project, the procedures and requirements of the potential finder, and the number of funders involved.

3. Pilots’ PDA Managing Teams

The pilots worked on the provided tool (presented in section 2.1) on their PDA structure for setting-up their Managing Teams, based on their specific needs.

Each one of the four PDA Managing Teams included experts with:

- administrative issues,
- financial aspects,
- legal issues,
- technical aspects,
- risks mitigation,
- evaluation, monitoring and validation
- other (identified by each partner)

The tables below present the DECISO PDA Managing Teams members for the 4 pilots.

Table 3 - DECISO PDA Managing Teams members set-up – Pilot 1: Hamburg

	Number	Name and position in PDA team (external experts in cyan)	Years of experience	Specific Tasks - Responsibilities (as described in WP3)
Administrative issues	2	Sabine Herrmann Project manager	9	Coordinating activities, stakeholder engagement, market research, monitoring & evaluation

(including management)		Thomas Jacob Project developer	>20		Project development communication plan
Financial aspects	2	Sabine Schubbe Financial Manager	>15		Budget planning, financial forecast
		Founding expert, Investment and Founding Bank Hamburg	>10		Project financing, bridge between the public sector and banking sector
Legal issues	1	Thomas Jacob Project developer	>20		Legal and regulatory guidance, project maturity assessment
Technical aspects	3	Advisor Green Economy, Environmental Authority Hamburg	>15		Technical project development, market analysis, procurement support
		Green Economy expert, Environmental Authority Hamburg	>10		Circular Business Network, concept development support
		Advisor at HiiCCE (Hamburg Institute for Innovation, Climate Protection, and Circular Economy)	>10		Technical project development, focus on circular furniture; life cycle assessment
Risks mitigation	2	Project manager, TUTECH Innovation GMBH	>20		Risk assessment, risk monitoring, risk planning
		Advisor, Hamburg, Institute of International Economics (HWWI)	>20		Risk identification, risk control implementation

Table 4 - DECISO PDA Managing Teams members set-up – Pilot 2: Alentejo

	Number	Name and position in PDA team (external experts in cyan)	Years of experience	Specific Tasks - Responsibilities (as described in WP3)
Administrative issues (including management)	2	Rosa Onofre Project manager	+20	Coordinating activities overall project management activities
		Joana Sabino Project developer	+ 5	Stakeholder engagement, monitoring & evaluation
Financial aspects	2	IRRADIARE		Business plan
		External expert		Financial plan
Legal issues	1	Nouno Sousa	+ 8	Legal and regulatory guidance

Technical aspects	2	Sofia Martins and IAPMEI	+20	Technical project development, market analysis, procurement support
Risks mitigation	1	IRRADIARE		Methodology to assure the impact and crosscutting themes of circular economy
Finance research Communication	2	Joana Sabino and Luís Rodrigues	+ 8	Identify potential finance instruments to support potential projects
		Tiago Godinho		Promotion of dialogue and engagement

Table 5 - DECISO PDA Managing Teams members set-up – Pilot 3: Northwestern Germany

	Number	Name and position in PDA team (no external experts)	Years of experience	Specific Tasks - Responsibilities (as described in WP3)
Administrative issues (including management)	1	Daniel Gerdes Project Manager	8	Coordinating activities, stakeholder engagement, monitoring & evaluation, overall project management activities
Financial aspects	1	Daniel Gerdes Project Manager	8	Budget planning for proposals
Legal issues	1	Konstantin Scheihing Specialist Water Management and Water Rights	>15	Legal and regulatory guidance, project maturity assessment
Technical aspects	2	Julia Oberdörffer and Konstantin Scheihing Technical Project lead climate adaptation	>15	Technical project development, technical design, stakeholder management
Risks mitigation	2	Konstantin Scheihing and Daniel Gerdes	>8	Scientific project assistance & Risk monitoring

Table 6 - DECISO PDA Managing Teams members set-up – Pilot 4: Western Macedonia

	Number	Name and position in PDA team (external experts in cyan)	Years of experience	Specific Tasks - Responsibilities (as described in WP3)
Administrative issues (including management)	2	Kyriakopoulos Konstantinos Project manager	>15	Coordinating activities, Concept development support, monitoring & evaluation, Greek Green Fund project contact
		Vogli Nicoletta Project developer	>15	Project development, stakeholder engagement, communication plan
Financial aspects	2	Karypides Theodoros Financial Manager	>15	Budget planning, Quality assurance, market research
		Efthymiou Foteini Financial expert	>10	Project financing, financial administration

Legal issues	1	Vogli Nicoletta Project developer	>15	Legal and regulatory guidance, project maturity assessment
Technical aspects	3	Palios Anastasios District heating expert	>15	Technical project development, market analysis, procurement support
		Samaras Symeon District heating expert	>15	Engineering, procurement and implementation support
		Krestou Athina Circular Economy expert (UoWM)	>20	Scientific project assistance with a focus on circular economy aspects
Risks mitigation	1	Karamarkos Konstantinos Strategic planner	>30	Scientific project assistance & Risk monitoring

Comment:

The Managing Teams will be mainly composed of personnel of the promoters, while some activities require external experts (marked in cyan letters).

4. Governance structure and processes

The pilots worked on their PDA model for planning the operative steps of each pilot of the Managing Teams governance structure model (following the tool that is presented in section 2.2).

The core objective of the PDA (Project Development Assistance) Managing Teams within the DECISO project is to facilitate the successful initiation, development, and monitoring of circular economy projects across the pilot regions. This involves several key responsibilities aligned with the operational structure and the functionalities of the PDA tool.

Firstly, the teams are responsible for identifying and leveraging opportunities. This involves discovering project opportunities through funding calls and legal frameworks that align with the pilot regions' programme ambitions. By ensuring that each pilot region capitalizes on these opportunities, the teams help develop relevant and impactful projects.

Secondly, the PDA Managing Teams provide tailored support. They offer specialized services such as legal assistance, risk identification and mitigation, and funding source identification to enhance project viability and sustainability. The PDA tool is utilized to deliver these services effectively, ensuring that all regions receive the necessary support to progress their initiatives.

Monitoring and evaluation form the third key responsibility. The teams use the Excel-based PDA tracking system to monitor the progress of each pilot region's projects. They conduct regular (six-monthly) review meetings to assess project performance, share lessons learned, and review key indicators, risks, and legal opportunities.

Facilitating collaboration and knowledge sharing is another crucial aspect of the teams' work. They organize and lead bi-annual review meetings that bring together representatives from all pilot regions and service providers. These meetings encourage the exchange of best practices, success stories, and challenges, fostering a collaborative learning environment among the regions.

Finally, ensuring alignment with program goals is essential. The teams make sure that all projects align with the overarching goals and objectives of the DECISO project and the specific ambitions of each pilot region. They regularly review and update project strategies to reflect evolving programme goals and emerging opportunities.

By focusing on these objectives, the PDA Managing Teams play a crucial role in driving the successful implementation of circular economy projects, enhancing regional collaboration, and ensuring continuous improvement across all pilot regions.

Establishing a governance structure is critical for the success of any project. This structure helps define the roles, responsibilities, and decision-making processes to ensure accountability, transparency, and effective collaboration among the Managing Team members.

Each following governance structure defines roles, responsibilities, and decision-making processes. Each DECISO pilot established a governance structure for the pilot implementation, that includes the Processes (P) described in the following tables:

Table 7 - Governance structure for the pilot implementation in Hamburg

DESICO Pilot 1: Hamburg PDA Processes Structure
P1. Monitoring the Key goals – indicators & the projects’ alignment with the organisation
Objectives of the process: To overview the: Key goals – indicators to achieve as planned for the project and to manage the: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Project alignment with organisational strategy, risk management, compliance, and efficient decision-making.
Responsible PDA members for P1: Sabine Herrmann, Thomas Jacob
P2. Monitoring the Coordination with the Key Stakeholders
Objective of the process: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> To monitor the coordination with the identified relevant key stakeholders list (input from WP2)
Responsible PDA members for P2: Thomas Jacob, Sabine Schubbe
P3. Monitoring the projects’ Roles and Responsibilities
Objectives of the process: To overview & monitor the Specific roles and Responsibilities' effectiveness: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Project Manager: Responsible for day-to-day planning, execution, and monitoring of the project. Project Team Members: Carry out specific tasks and contribute to the project's overall success. Steering Committee: Provides strategic guidance and decision-making authority.
Responsible PDA members for P3: Sabine Herrmann, Thomas Jacob
P4. Monitoring the projects’ Decision-Making Processes
Objectives of the process: To overview & monitor the activities foreseen: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Levels of authority for different roles Decisions require approval from higher levels
Responsible PDA members for P4: Sabine Herrmann, Thomas Jacob
P5. Monitoring the projects’ Risk Management
Objective of the process:

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overview & monitor the projects’ risk management plan
Responsible PDA members for P5: Sabine Herrmann, Advisors of Environmental Authorities
P6. Monitoring the Projects’ Internal Communication Plan
Objectives of the process: Overview & monitor the activities foreseen, in terms of: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Frequency • Channels of communication • Types of information to be communicated
Responsible PDA members for P6: Sabine Herrmann, Thomas Jacob
P7. Monitoring the Meeting Protocols
Objective of the process: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overview & monitor the protocols for meetings, including frequency, agenda creation, and reporting mechanisms.
Responsible PDA member for P7: Sabine Herrmann

Table 8 - Governance structure for the pilot implementation in Alentejo

DESICO Pilot 2: Alentejo PDA Processes Structure
P1. Monitoring the Key goals – indicators & the projects’ alignment with the organisation
Objectives of the process: To overview the: Key goals – indicators to achieve as planned for the project and to manage the: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project alignment with organisational strategy, risk management, compliance, and efficient decision-making.
Responsible PDA member for P1: Rosa Onofre
P2. Monitoring the Coordination with the Key Stakeholders
Objective of the process: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To monitor the coordination with the identified relevant key stakeholders list (input from WP2)
Responsible PDA member for P2: Joana Sabino
P3. Monitoring the projects’ Roles and Responsibilities
Objectives of the process: To overview & monitor the Specific roles and Responsibilities' effectiveness: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project Manager: Responsible for day-to-day planning, execution, and monitoring of the project. • Project Team Members: Carry out specific tasks and contribute to the project's overall success. • Steering Committee: Provides strategic guidance and decision-making authority.
Responsible PDA members for P3: Rosa Onofre and Joana Sabino
P4. Monitoring the projects’ Decision-Making Processes
Objectives of the process: To overview & monitor the activities foreseen: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Levels of authority for different roles • Decisions require approval from higher levels
Responsible PDA member for P4: Joana Sabino
P5. Monitoring the projects’ Risk Management
Objective of the process: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overview & monitor the projects’ risk management plan
Responsible PDA member for P5: Sara Balcazar

<p>P6. Monitoring the Projects’ Internal Communication Plan</p> <p>Objectives of the process: Overview & monitor the activities foreseen, in terms of:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Frequency • Channels of communication • Types of information to be communicated <p>Responsible PDA member for P6: Tiago Godinho</p>
<p>P7. Monitoring the Meeting Protocols</p> <p>Objective of the process:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overview & monitor the protocols for meetings, including frequency, agenda creation, and reporting mechanisms. <p>Responsible PDA member for P7: Nuno Sousa</p>

Table 9 - Governance structure for the pilot implementation in Northwestern Germany

DESICO Pilot 3: Northwestern Germany PDA Processes Structure
<p>P1. Monitoring the Key goals – indicators & the projects’ alignment with the organisation</p> <p>Objectives of the process: To overview the: Key goals – indicators to achieve as planned for the project and to manage the:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project alignment with organisational strategy, risk management, compliance, and efficient decision-making. <p>Responsible PDA members for P1: Daniel Gerdes, Julia Oberdörffer</p>
<p>P2. Monitoring the Coordination with the Key Stakeholders</p> <p>Objective of the process:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To monitor the coordination with the identified relevant key stakeholders list (input from WP2) <p>Responsible PDA members for P2: Daniel Gerdes, Julia Oberdörffer</p>
<p>P3. Monitoring the projects’ Roles and Responsibilities</p> <p>Objectives of the process: To overview & monitor the Specific roles and Responsibilities' effectiveness:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project Manager: Responsible for day-to-day planning, execution, and monitoring of the project. • Project Team Members: Carry out specific tasks and contribute to the project's overall success. • Steering Committee: Provides strategic guidance and decision-making authority. <p>Responsible PDA members for P3: Daniel Gerdes, Julia Oberdörffer</p>
<p>P4. Monitoring the projects’ Decision-Making Processes</p> <p>Objectives of the process: To overview & monitor the activities foreseen:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Levels of authority for different roles • Decisions require approval from higher levels <p>Responsible PDA member for P4: Daniel Gerdes</p>
<p>P5. Monitoring the projects’ Risk Management</p> <p>Objective of the process:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overview & monitor the projects’ risk management plan <p>Responsible PDA member for P5: Daniel Gerdes</p>
<p>P6. Monitoring the Projects’ Internal Communication Plan</p> <p>Objectives of the process:</p>

Overview & monitor the activities foreseen, in terms of: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Frequency • Channels of communication • Types of information to be communicated
Responsible PDA members for P6: Sabine Gerdes, Julia Oberdörffer
P7. Monitoring the Meeting Protocols
Objective of the process: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overview & monitor the protocols for meetings, including frequency, agenda creation, and reporting mechanisms.
Responsible PDA member for P7: Daniel Gerdes

Table 10 - Governance structure for the pilot implementation in Western Macedonia

DESICO Pilot 4: Western Macedonia PDA Processes Structure
P1. Monitoring the Key goals – indicators & the projects' alignment with the organisation
Objectives of the process: To overview the: Key goals – indicators to achieve as planned for the project and to manage the: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project alignment with organisational strategy, risk management, compliance, and efficient decision-making.
Responsible PDA member for P1: Kyriakopoulos Konstantinos
P2. Monitoring the Coordination with the Key Stakeholders
Objective of the process: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To monitor the coordination with the identified relevant key stakeholders list (input from WP2)
Responsible PDA members for P2: Vogli Nicoletta, Palios Anastasios
P3. Monitoring the projects' Roles and Responsibilities
Objectives of the process: To overview & monitor the Specific roles and Responsibilities' effectiveness: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project Manager: Responsible for day-to-day planning, execution, and monitoring of the project. • Project Team Members: Carry out specific tasks and contribute to the project's overall success. • Steering Committee: Provides strategic guidance and decision-making authority.
Responsible PDA members for P3: Kyriakopoulos Konstantinos, Samaras Symeon
P4. Monitoring the projects' Decision-Making Processes
Objectives of the process: To overview & monitor the activities foreseen: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Levels of authority for different roles • Decisions require approval from higher levels
Responsible PDA member for P4: Karypides Theodoros
P5. Monitoring the projects' Risk Management
Objective of the process: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overview & monitor the projects' risk management plan
Responsible PDA member for P5: Palios Anastasios
P6. Monitoring the Projects' Internal Communication Plan
Objectives of the process: Overview & monitor the activities foreseen, in terms of: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Frequency

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Channels of communication • Types of information to be communicated
Responsible PDA member for P6: Vogli Nicoletta
P7. Monitoring the Meeting Protocols
Objective of the process: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overview & monitor the protocols for meetings, including frequency, agenda creation, and reporting mechanisms.
Responsible PDA member for P7: Efthymiou Foteini

Comment: All pilots are able to replace their PDA members, responsible for specific processes during their projects' implementation.

Figure 4: Graph of all DECISO Pilots Processes

- P1: Monitoring the Key goals – indicators & the projects’ alignment with the organisation
- P2: Monitoring the Coordination with the Key Stakeholders
- P3: Monitoring the projects’ Roles and Responsibilities
- P4: Monitoring the projects’ Decision-Making Processes
- P5: Monitoring the projects’ Risk Management
- P6: Monitoring the Projects’ Internal Communication Plan
- P7: Monitoring the Meeting Protocols

5. ANNEX - Set-up managing teams & related D4.1 Framework

Table 11 - DECISO PDA Managing Teams members set-up – Pilot X

	Number	Name and position in PDA team (for external experts’ colour in cyan)	Years of experience	Specific Tasks - Responsibilities (as described in WP3)
Administrative issues (including management)		Name – Position		
Financial aspects		Name – Position		
Legal issues		Name – Position		
Technical aspects		Name – Position		
Risks mitigation		Name – Position		
Other		Name – Position		

Examples of DECISO PDA Managing teams’ tasks and responsibilities:

Due diligence assessment

- Project maturity assessment
- Technical due diligence
- Bankability assessment

Financial services

- Business plan and financial plans
- Market analysis
- Financial forecasts

Technical services

- Support in the preparation of applications
- Concept development support
- Economic analysis
- Engineering, procurement and implementation support

Examples of DESICO PDA Managing teams' activities:

Independent reviews

- Support in the preparation of applications
- Concept development support
- Economic analysis
- Engineering, procurement and implementation support

Additional studies

- Market research
- Life cycle assessment (LCA)
- Stakeholder analysis
- Resource planning
- Communication plan
- Quality assurance

Financial modelling

- Review of the existing financial model
- Development of a bank-standard financial model
- Business case modelling

Other Financial Advisory

- Business plan assessment
- Corporate strategy guidance
- Advice on fundraising strategy
- Support with equity pitch documentation

6. Bibliography and sitography

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